

growth were less in the plots that received ammonium sulfate than in the plots that received urea. Ammonium sulfate also helped decompose weeds. Urea applied a week after crop plowing did not

influence weed decomposition, so most of the weeds re-established. Grain yields were also remarkably increased. Average grain yield was 3.26 t/ha for the ammonium sulfate treatment, and

2.4 t/ha for urea. Since no additional input costs are involved, extension agencies may consider suggesting the method to farmers. ■

Influence of soil moisture regime on iron and manganese release in soil and on the growth of upland rice

R. S. Khaire and K. R. Sonar, Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Mahatma Phule Agricultural University, Rahuri 413 722, Maharashtra, India

A pot experiment, conducted on Vertic Ustropepts (medium black clay: pH 8.5; CaCO₃, 6.0%; and organic carbon, 0.5%)

in the 1977 rainy season, studied the influence of soil saturation and submergence for 10 and 20 days before sowing on the supply of iron and manganese in the soil and on the dry matter yield of upland rice. The variety used was Karjat 184.

The iron and manganese supply in the soil increased with the duration of soil saturation or submergence (see table). The increase may have been caused by

moderately reduced soil conditions that resulted from soil saturation or submergence before sowing (Eh values decreased from 501 mV to 369 mV and pH decreased from 8.6 to 7.6). Iron and manganese contents in the soil were higher after submergence for 10 or 20 days than after soil saturation. The dry-matter yield increased — probably because of the higher supply of iron and manganese. ■

Iron and manganese contents in soil and dry matter yield of rice as influenced by soil moisture regimes before sowing. Mean of 5 replications. Maharashtra, India

Soil water treatment before sowing	Iron content (ppm)		Manganese content (ppm)		Dry matter yield of rice at harvest (g/5 plants per pot)
	Initial (immediately after soil water treatment)	Final (at the end of soil water treatment period 10 or 20 days)	Initial (immediately after soil water treatment)	Final (at the end of soil water treatment period)	
Soil saturation, 10 days	2.4	2.6	0.7	1.0	5.3
Soil submergence, 10 days	2.6	3.2	0.7	1.3	7.6
Soil saturation, 20 days	2.4	3.6	0.7	1.2	7.5
Soil submergence, 20 days	2.6	4.1	0.7	2.1	8.9
Control (dry soil)	1.2	1.2	0.7	0.7	5.2

A simple test for available zinc and copper in wetland rice soils

R. S. Lantin, senior research assistant; M. T. C. Cayton, research assistant; and F. N. Ponnampuruma, principal soil chemist, Soil Chemistry Department, International Rice Research Institute

Zinc deficiency is a widespread nutritional disorder of wetland rice. It occurs on alkali, calcareous, poorly drained mineral, and peat soils. Copper deficiency limits rice yields on peat soils and also, perhaps, on other zinc-deficient soils. The need for simple, rapid, and reliable method for estimating zinc and copper in soils used for wetland rice is pressing.

Because the widely used DTPA and EDTA methods consume too much time and chemicals, 0.1 N HCl and 0.05 N HCl as extractants for available zinc and copper were compared with DTPA and

EDTA in a laboratory and greenhouse study of 32 soils covering a wide range of pH and organic matter content.

The 0.1 N HCl method consisted of shaking 2 g air-dry soil with 20 ml 0.1 N HCl for 5 minutes. The 0.05 N HCl method used 10 g air-dry soil, 20 ml 0.05 N HCl, and 5 minutes shaking. The extracts were filtered and zinc and copper determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry, along with the DTPA and EDTA extracts obtained by shaking for 2 hours and 30 minutes, respectively. Rice plants grown on the flooded soils were wet-ashed and the concentrations of zinc and copper measured.

The 0.05 N HCl method gave the best correlation between extractable zinc and copper and their concentration in the plant:

Method	Concn of element in extract vs concn in plant	
	Zn	Cu
ESDTA-(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃	.43**	.28ns
DTPA/TEA	.31 ns	.20ns
0.1 N HCl	.55**	.64**
0.05 N HCl	.88**	.74**

On 13 of the 16 soils that contained less than 1 ppm Zn extractable with 0.05 N HCl, plants showed zinc deficiency symptoms or contained < 27 ppm zinc. Although no copper deficiency symptoms were recognized, plants growing on 13 of 15 soils with <0.1 ppm Cu by the 0.05 N HCl method contained < 5 ppm copper.

Available zinc (0.05 N HCl) correlated highly with available copper (0.05 N HCl) with $r = .58^{**}$. So did plant zinc and